

NOTES

Preparation and Characterisation of some Pentacoordinated Mixed-ligand Complexes of Cobalt(II) and Nickel(II)

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THE preparation and characterisation of mixed-ligand pentacoordinated complexes of cobalt(II) and nickel(II) with phthalimide (P) and succinimide (S) as monodentate, and diethylenetriamine (dien) and terpyridyl (terpy) as tridentate ligands on the basis of elemental analysis, ir, electronic spectra, conductance and magnetic measurements are described.

Experimental

Infrared spectra (film) were recorded on a Beckman IR-20 spectrophotometer. The electronic spectra were recorded on a DU-6 UV-VIS spectrophotometer. Magnetic measurements were carried out on a PAR 155 vibrating sample magnetometer. Conductivity measurements were carried out on a Systronic 302 conductivity bridge.

Phthalimide and succinimide (Koch light), terpyridyl (Fluka, AG) and diethylenetriamine (Riedel) were used. All other chemicals were of AnalaR grade.

Preparation of complexes: Ethanolic solutions (0.02 M) of metal chloride, potassium salt of succinimide or phthalimide and the amine (terpyridyl

or diethylenetriamine) were mixed in the molar ratio of 1 : 2 : 1 and allowed to stand for ~20 min. The precipitated potassium chloride was filtered off. The filtrate was heated to ~60° for 1 h and then kept aside for 5 h. The resulting crystalline precipitate was filtered, washed with ethanol and dried.

Results and Discussion

Metal, carbon, hydrogen and nitrogen analyses and the molar conductance data of cobalt(II) complexes in dimethylsulphoxide and of nickel(II) complexes in dimethylformamide are given in Table 1. The molar conductances indicate non-electrolytic nature of the complexes.

Ir spectra: Imide ion which is a common constituent of all the complexes has two frequency regions (NH and CO) of intense absorption. The ir spectra could not make a sharp distinction whether coordination is through nitrogen or oxygen of the carbonyl group because any change in the imide nitrogen which is directly linked to the carbonyl group will alter the molecular environment and hence the frequency of the latter even if it is not coordinated¹. Secondly, the filled orbital of the imide nitrogen is made available by quasi-aromatic delocalisation which would give a lower bond order to C=O and a lower frequency. However, on the basis of Lewis acid concept it may be assumed that the negatively charged imide nitrogen will have better possibility of being coordinated than oxygen². Further, there will be steric hindrance if coordination is through oxygen. There was shifting of two bands due to carbonyl groups

TABLE I—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPLEXES

Sl. no.	Compd.*	Colour	Analysis % · Found/(Calcd.)				Molar conductances $\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$
			Metal	C	H	N	
1.	[Co(P) ₂ (terpy)]	Chocolate	10.09 (10.96)	63.68 (63.79)	3.25 (3.00)	11.98 (12.75)	10
2.	[Ni(P) ₂ (terpy)]	Blue	10.05 (11.00)	63.70 (64.31)	3.25 (2.97)	11.99 (11.39)	15
3.	[Co(S) ₂ (terpy)]	Chocolate	12.07 (12.59)	56.53 (57.05)	3.89 (4.15)	14.34 (15.31)	15
4.	[Ni(S) ₂ (terpy)]	Blue	12.03 (11.77)	56.56 (56.31)	3.89 (3.79)	14.34 (15.27)	11
5.	[Co(P) ₂ (dien)]	Chocolate	12.98 (13.69)	52.87 (53.59)	4.63 (4.41)	15.42 (14.77)	5
6.	[Ni(P) ₂ (dien)]	Violet	12.94 (13.78)	52.90 (53.78)	4.63 (4.98)	15.43 (16.16)	11
7.	[Co(S) ₂ (dien)]	Chocolate	16.46 (15.79)	40.23 (41.02)	5.87 (6.29)	19.56 (20.43)	9
8.	[Ni(S) ₂ (dien)]	Violet	16.41 (17.39)	40.26 (40.38)	5.87 (6.71)	19.57 (19.19)	15

* P=C₈H₄NO₂, S=C₄H₄NO₂, terpy=C₁₁H₁₁N₃ and dien=C₄H₁₁N₃.

from 1 780 and 1 750 cm^{-1} (free ligand) to $\sim 1 650$ and 1 620 cm^{-1} respectively, in the spectra of the complexes. The coordination via oxygen would give rise to a large difference in the fundamental stretching frequencies of the two carbonyl groups and one band would be shifted far more than the other by metal ion coordination. The fact that the frequencies of the two bands are lowered by an equivalent amount on coordination, suggests that the coordination occurred through nitrogen. A strong band at 3 300 cm^{-1} due to NH of imide changed into a band of negligible intensity in the spectra of their salts, indicates the deprotonation of imide group. This negative shift may be due to the mass effect⁹. The stretching frequency at 1 470 cm^{-1} due to C-N in the spectra of imides also shifted to $\sim 1 500 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the spectra of the complexes, indicating thereby the coordination of the imide ion with the metal ion⁴.

The characteristic ring vibrations of heterocyclic bases (terpyridyl) in the range 1 600–1 450 cm^{-1} generally show significant changes on complexation⁵ which could not be distinguished because of mixing or overlapping with C=O and C-N stretching bands in the complexes 1–4. The in-plane and out-of-plane ring deformation modes in these cases observed near 500 and 700 cm^{-1} , respectively, in the free ligand undergo a positive shift in the complexes which is usual for coordination through nitrogen⁵. The absence of the bands due to ν_{OH} ruled out the possibility of formation of solvated complex, i.e. $[\text{Mn}_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})]$ or $[\text{Mn}_2(\text{EtOH})]$.

Magnetic moments and electronic spectra: The magnetic moment values of the nickel(II) complexes lie in the range 2.60–2.70 B.M. at room temperature. The values are lower than that expected for nickel(II) complexes⁶, but a few such observations are available at present^{7,8}. The magnetic moment values of cobalt(II) complexes are in the range 3.99–4.12 B.M. at room temperature. These values are considerably lower than that predicted for tetrahedral (4.40–4.87 B.M.) or octahedral (4.70–5.20 B.M.) complexes at room temperature^{9,10}.

The electronic spectra of nickel(II) complexes in dimethylformamide showed four bands in the range 8 100–8 700 (ν_1), 10 200–11 000 (ν_2), 14 500–16 000 (ν_3), 22 500–23 500 (ν_4) cm^{-1} , while cobalt(II) complexes in dimethylsulphoxide gave three bands in the range 9 200–10 650 (ν_1), 16 800–17 500 (ν_2) and 22 200–23 250 (ν_3) cm^{-1} . The presence of these bands at nearly the same positions was also observed in the spectra of the solid compounds, which indicated no dissociation of the complexes in solution and also not identifying them as polymeric solids with coordination number six. The four- or six-coordinated complexes of these metal ions do not give the bands in this range¹¹. However, these spectral bands resemble the spectra of five-coordinate complexes¹² whose structures have been established by X-ray measurements.

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Possible Different Behaviour of 4,4'-(4,4'-Biphenylenebisazo)-di(2-hydroxyacetophenone) in its Copper(II), Zinc(II) Iron(II), Iron(III) and Dioxouranium(VI) Chelates

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WE have the properties of polychelates derived by polymerising monomeric symmetric tetra-functioning ligands through metal ion¹. Here, in an attempt to prepare such polychelates of 4,4'-(4,4'-biphenylenebisazo)-di(2-hydroxyacetophenone) (L), we have obtained such polychelates for Fe^{II} and Fe^{III} , Cu^{II} gives dinuclear chelate of the formula $\text{Cu}_2\text{L}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot (\text{H}_2\text{O})_6$, while mononuclear chelates for UO_2^{II} and Zn^{II} . In the first case the polychelates have been obtained by polymerisation of L through metal ion in which L is tetra-functioning. In the second case L is tetra-functioning without any further polymerisation while in the last case it is bifunctioning. The preparation of the ligand and all the physicochemical measurements were made as described earlier².

Preparation of complexes: To a refluxing ligand solution (2.5 mmol in 80 ml DMF), a well stirred metal salt solution (2.5 mmol in 60 ml DMF) was added followed by sodium acetate (~ 2.0 g) and the resulting mixture was allowed to reflux for 3 h. The complexes thus obtained were filtered and washed with hot DMF, hot water and ethanol and dried at 40°.

Results and Discussion

The analytical data of the chelates are presented in Table 1. The Fe^{II} and Fe^{III} chelates suggest 1 : {